

BPFM Evaluation

This evaluation requires performing a series of tasks using the BPFM (Business Process Family Management) software. The application allows managing variability in business process families with different languages and the automatic generation of variants based on specific configurations. Completing the tasks and filling in the associated form should not take more than 30 minutes.

***Obligatorio**

Guidelines for accessing BPFM and performing the evaluation

The document with the tasks to be carried out for the BPFM evaluation, and the files to be used, are available at <https://bit.ly/3iqXvqf>. The BPFM application can be accessed at <https://bit.ly/3wXIG2K>.

The scale for the evaluation is from 1 to 5, where 1 is the lowest value, and 5 is the highest value.

BPFM Functionality

1. Variety of variability approaches - does the application provide an adequate variety of variability approaches and languages? *

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- 1 - The variety of variability approaches provided is not adequate
- 2 - The variety of variability approaches provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The variety of variability approaches provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The variety of variability approaches provided is adequate
- 5 - The variety of variability approaches provided is very adequate

2. Justify your answer on the variety of variability approaches provided by the application *

3. Work methodology - does the application provide a user-friendly guide so that the user can carry out the tasks? *

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- 1 - The work methodology provided is not adequate
- 2 - The work methodology provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The work methodology provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The work methodology provided is adequate
- 5 - The work methodology provided is very adequate

4. Justify your answer on the work methodology provided by the application *

5. Import / Export of models - does the application provide a feature for import / export of models? *

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- 1 - The import / export feature provided is not adequate
- 2 - The import / export feature provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The import / export feature provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The import / export feature provided is adequate
- 5 - The import / export feature provided is very adequate

6. Justify your answer on the import / export of models provided by the application *

7. Model validation - does the application support model validation? *

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- 1 - The model validation support provided is not adequate
- 2 - The model validation support provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The model validation support provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The model validation support provided is adequate
- 5 - The model validation support provided is very adequate

8. Justify your answer on the model validation features provided by the application *

9. Variant configuration - does the application allow defining a configuration for a specific process variant?

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- 1 - The variant configuration support provided is not adequate
- 2 - The variant configuration support provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The variant configuration support provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The variant configuration support provided is adequate
- 5 - The variant configuration support provided is very adequate

10. Justify your answer on the variant configuration support provided by the application *

11. Variation generation - does the application provide automatic generation of variants based on a specific configuration? *

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- 1 - The variant generation support provided is not adequate
- 2 - The variant generation support provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The variant generation support provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The variant generation support provided is adequate
- 5 - The variant generation support provided is very adequate

12. Justify your answer on the generation of variants support provided by the application *
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13. Version control - does the application provide version control over the models, configurations and process variants? *

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- 1 - The version control provided is not adequate
- 2 - The version control provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The version control provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The version control provided is adequate
- 5 - The version control provided is very adequate

14. Justify your answer on the version control provided by the application *

15. Collaborative work - does the application allow collaborative work on a process family?

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- 1 - The collaborative work support provided is not adequate
- 2 - The collaborative work support provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The collaborative work support provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The collaborative work support provided is adequate
- 5 - The collaborative work support provided is very adequate

16. Justify your answer on the collaborative work support provided by the application *

BPFM Usability

17. User interface - is the user interface easy to navigate, and does it present results in a meaningful way? *

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- 1 - The user interface provided is not adequate
- 2 - The user interface provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The user interface provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The user interface provided is adequate
- 5 - The user interface provided is very adequate

18. Justify your answer on the user interface provided by the application *

19. Learning curve - is the application easy to learn? (novice user), or, is the application easy to use? (advanced user) *

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- 1 - The learning curve is not adequate
- 2 - The learning curve is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The learning curve is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The learning curve is adequate
- 5 - The learning curve is very adequate

20. Justify your answer on the application's learning curve *

21. Data visualization - how well does the application present the involved data and models? *

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- 1 - The data visualization provided is not adequate
- 2 - The data visualization provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The data visualization provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The data visualization provided is adequate
- 5 - The data visualization provided is very adequate

22. Justify your answer on the data visualization features provided by the application *

23. Error report - how meaningful is the error report provided by the application? *

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- 1 - The error report provided is not adequate
- 2 - The error report provided is somewhat adequate
- 3 - The error report provided is neither adequate nor inadequate
- 4 - The error report provided is adequate
- 5 - The error report provided is very adequate

24. Justify your answer on the error report provided by the application *

Participant Data

25. Copy the generated UUID that identifies the family you have defined within BPFM *

26. Country of residence *

27. Contact e-mail (optional)

28. Please indicate your work area *

29. What is the highest level of education you have completed? *

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- 1 - Tertiary education
- 2 - Undergraduate degree (University)
- 3 - master's degree
- 4 - Doctoral degree
- 5 - None of the above

30. Indicate your level of knowledge about variability and business process families *

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- 1 - I have no knowledge
- 2 - I have minimal knowledge
- 3 - I have an intermediate knowledge
- 4 - I have a good knowledge
- 5 - I have a very good knowledge

31. Other comments

Google no creó ni aprobó este contenido.

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